

SCRATCH AND COMPUTATIONAL THINKING: A COMPUTER PROGRAMMING INITIATIVE IN A GIRLS PRIMARY SCHOOL

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In recent years there has been an unprecedented push to improve the quality of education, and revitalise interest, in STEM. In this context, Computational Thinking has emerged as an essential twenty-first century competence, as fundamental as reading, writing and arithmetic (Wing, 2006). Mathematics has been identified as a field which can foster the development of computational thinking and the NCCA have committed to embedding computational thinking in the new primary curriculum. Educators and researchers have adopted two main approaches to teaching computational thinking: plugged activities (programming) and unplugged activities (without technology). The aim of this research is to assess what benefits, particularly in relation to computational thinking, can be gained from the use of a visual programming language, Scratch, in a girls primary school. Brennan and Resnick (2012) developed a computational thinking framework that examines three key dimensions of computational thinking: computational concepts, computational practices, and computational perspectives. Using this framework, this study examined the development of students' computational thinking skills during a ten week programming initiative. Data were collected from Project Portfolios Analysis, Design Scenarios and Participant Observation. This paper describes the findings of this research study in relation to one of the key dimensions of computational thinking: computational concepts, developed by the participants as a result of engaging in the programming initiative.

INTRODUCTION

In the face of unpredictable and unprecedented change, European and International policies have acknowledged the importance of developing education systems responsive to the demands of a knowledge-based society. For example, the eEurope 2002 Action Plan observed that 21st century schools require curricula to develop different knowledge, skills and dispositions than those required in the 20th century. Computational thinking is a problem-solving process, which originated in the field of computer science but is increasingly being recognised as an essential competency for all fields. In 2006, Jeannette Wing wrote an influential article on computational thinking, giving a 21st century perspective to the concept. She advocated for adding this new competency to every child's analytical ability, describing it as a vital ingredient of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) learning. Cuny, Snyder & Wing (2010) describe computational thinking as:

The thought processes involved in formulating problems and their solutions so that the solutions are represented in a form that can be effectively carried out by an information-processing agent (p. 1).

Wing's arguments captured the attention of a broad academic community and since then computational thinking has become a catchphrase, as government education advisors and curriculum developers explore possible directions for 21st century appropriate curricula. In the

Action Plan for Education 2017, the Irish government announced their intention to reform the primary mathematics curriculum, to include computational thinking, creative thinking skills and programming. However, despite considerable international interest in integrating computational thinking to school curricula, its successful integration still faces several challenges, as identified in a report by the ET 2020 Working Group on Digital Skills and Competences (EC, 2016, p. 1):

Is CT a skill that benefits all living in an increasingly digital world?

What features characterise CT instruction?

How does the concept of CT and CT instruction relate to programming/coding, computer science and digital literacy?

How should CT be assessed?

How can teachers be prepared to successfully integrate CT into their teaching practice?

COMPUTATIONAL THINKING IN THE CURRICULUM

Introducing computational thinking to the primary school curriculum, as with the introduction of any new content, brings with it both challenges and possibilities. Teachers are required to equip themselves with both subject knowledge and pedagogical knowledge. With many countries introducing computer science as a core curriculum subject there has been a plethora of research studies, initiatives and policy reports on the topic. Inevitably, the content of curricula in each country will be different, however many of them are incorporating computational thinking. A review of computational thinking initiatives and studies reveals that educators and researchers have adopted two main approaches to teaching computational thinking in schools: plugged activities (computer programming) and unplugged activities (those that do not require the use of technology).

Unplugged Activities

Although many unplugged initiatives predate the rise to prominence of computational thinking, it has become apparent that the unplugged approach emphasises computational thinking (Bell et al., 2012). In the last five years, a small number of studies have reported on the effect of unplugged activities on the development of computational thinking in US classrooms. Many of these have looked at the development of computational thinking of students in middle and high school. There is a dearth of research on the use of unplugged activities to develop the computational thinking of primary school students. Two recent studies that have explored this approach are Faber, Wierdsma, Doornbos, van der Ven & de Vette (2017) and Brackmann, Román-González, Robles, Moreno-León, Casali & Barone (2017). Faber et al. (2017) conducted an exploratory study in twenty six schools in the Netherlands. They designed a series of six ninety-minute unplugged lessons, which were subsequently taught to students in their final year of primary school. They reported that the lessons elicited a positive reaction from both the teachers and students and suggested that the unplugged approach offered a viable alternative to programming. Brackmann et al. (2017) report on a quasi-experiment conducted in two primary schools in Spain. In each of the schools the students were divided into an experimental group who participated in the unplugged lessons and a control group who did not. They assessed the computational thinking

skills of both groups of students with a pre-test and a post-test. They found that the computational thinking skills of the students who had participated in the unplugged lessons improved significantly, whereas the skills of those in the control group did not.

Plugged Activities

When computers first became available in schools, there was great enthusiasm to teach children to program. The computer was viewed as an instructional tool, which could be used for the development of higher order thinking skills. Seymour Papert was one of the early advocates of teaching children to program. His research on computers and education was based on the belief that “*children can learn to use computers in a masterful way, and that learning to use computers can change the way they learn everything else*” (Papert 1980, p.8). However, despite Papert’s claims, empirical studies failed to find conclusive evidence of this (Kurland, Pea, Clement & Mawby, 1986). Perhaps because of this, the use of computers in schools shifted away from the computer science approach towards a more computer literacy based approach. However, in recent years there has been some resurgence in the use of programming to develop higher order thinking skills in schools. This resurgence has been facilitated by the availability of numerous ‘low floor’ (easy to learn) programming languages have been developed specifically for novice programmers e.g. Scratch, Alice, Kodu, Toontalk and Stagecast Creator.

In a recent paper funded by the NCCA, Millwood, Bresnihan, Walsh and Hooper (2018) suggested a definition of Computational Thinking for use in the Irish education system:

“competence in problem solving & design to create useful solutions, informed by the possibilities that Computing offers” (p.8).

This definition suggests that students would exhibit competence in computational thinking by creating with technology. Hence, in this study the plugged approach was chosen as the preferred approach to teaching computational thinking.

Scratch Programming

The development of visual programming languages has provided more accessible ways for younger children to learn programming concepts (Koh, Basawapatna, Bennett, & Repenning, 2010). These languages often require programmers to drag-and-drop icons rather than type code. One such example is the Scratch programming language. Programs are written in Scratch by fitting ‘blocks’ together like pieces of a jigsaw puzzle (Wilson & Moffat, 2012). The blocks will only fit together in a certain way, so it eliminates the possibility of syntax errors. Even though Scratch is considered a ‘low floor’ programming language, it is also considered to be a ‘high ceiling’ (facilitates the creation of complex programs). It is also freely available, provides instant visual feedback and has an offline version, which is essential in areas with poor broadband connection. Therefore Scratch was chosen as the programming language for this study.

Assessing Computational Thinking

The rise in prominence of Scratch, as a key instrument in the development of computational thinking in educational settings, has led to the need for an assessment strategy to address the

evaluation of computational thinking of Scratch projects. Brennan and Resnick (2012) developed a computational thinking framework that examines three key dimensions of computational thinking: computational concepts, computational practices, and computational perspectives. Table 1 modified from Lye and Koh (2014) provides a brief summary of the key ideas of each dimension of computational thinking. For the purpose of this paper we will focus on the computational concepts developed by the participants as a result of engaging in the programming initiative.

Table 1: Key Dimensions of Computational Thinking (Lye & Koh, 2014 p. 53).

Dimension	Description	Examples
Computational concepts	Concepts that programmer(s) use	Variables Loops
Computational practices	Problem-solving practices that occurs in the process of programming	Being Incremental and Iterative, Testing and Debugging, Reusing and Remixing Abstracting and Modularizing
Computational perspectives	Students' understanding of themselves, their relationships to others, and the technological world around them.	Expressing and questioning about the technology world

New tools have been developed to assist educators in their assessment of computational thinking in such projects. One such tool is Dr Scratch, a free Web application powered by Hairball, which allows educators to analyse scratch projects by detecting bugs, verifying for the presence of programming constructs and assigning a computational thinking score.

OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRAMMING INITIATIVE

The method of enquiry employed in this study was Case Study Research. Participants were selected using convenience sampling. There were 90 participants from three classes in an urban, girl's, primary school. There were thirty-two third class students, twenty-eight fifth class students and thirty sixth class students. The majority of students had no prior programming experience. They worked in pairs or threes sharing one computer. The initiative took place over a ten week period, with one hour sessions each week, using the visual programming language Scratch. As outlined in Table 2, the first five sessions focussed on helping the children learn the basic functions while creating their first animations.

Table 2: Outline of the activities week by week

Week	Learning Objectives	Activity
1	Control, Movement and Coordinates.	Create an animation incorporating movement and images
2	Sequencing, Time, Iteration and Using Sounds.	Alternate sprite costumes, incorporating time and motion. Import, create and record sounds to use in their project
3	Motion, Direction, Rotation, Sensing and Broadcasting.	Create a joke or other short animation involving at least two characters.
4	Using Conditional Statements	Create a race animation or a pong game.
5	Variables, Time and Sensing.	Create a game which uses variables to record lives and score.

6-10	All previously learned skills.	Plan, create and edit your own Scratch project.
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In the following weeks there was no explicit programming instruction instead the sessions were run based on a ‘learning on demand’ model (Kafai & Ching, 2001) as pupils created their own animations. Various data collection methods were adopted in order to obtain the most comprehensive picture possible of the phenomena being studied. These included Project Portfolio Analysis, Artefact-Based Interviews, Design Scenarios (Brennan & Resnick, 2012) and Participant Observation. Project Portfolio were analysed using Dr Scratch to assign a computational thinking score determined by the competence demonstrated by the students in the seven computational concepts: abstraction and decomposition, logic, data representation, parallelism, synchronisation, flow control and user interactivity (Moreno-León & Robles, 2015). These concepts are explained further in Table 3.

Table 3: Definitions of Computational Thinking concepts (<http://www.drscratch.org/learn/Abstraction/>)

Concept	Definition
Abstraction and problem decomposition	Breaking a problem into smaller parts that are easier to understand, program and debug.
Logic	Instructions related to logical thinking that create a more dynamic program, so they behave differently depending on the situation.
Data Representation	The set of information about the characters in e.g. the position of each character, the direction it is pointing, size, etc. In addition data such as the level, elapsed time, the rating, the lives, the rewards collected.
Parallelism	Allows several things to occur simultaneously.
Synchronisation	Allow characters to organize things happen in the order we want
Flow Control	Control the behaviour of characters, e.g. certain blocks that are repeated a number of times or until a situation arises.
User Interactivity	The person who running the program can perform actions that provoke new situations in the project.

Each concept is given a score between 0-3 depending on the competence demonstrated in the project. The evaluation of these competences is based on the rules in Table 4.

Table 4: Competence Level for computational thinking concepts (Moreno-León & Robles, 2015 p. 6).

Computational Thinking Concept	Competence Level			
	Null (0)	Basic (1 point)	Developing (2 points)	Proficiency (3 points)
Abstraction and problem decomposition	-	More than one script and more than one sprite	Definition of blocks	Use of clones
Logic Thinking	-	If	If else	Logic operations
Data Representation	-	Modifiers of sprites properties	Operations on variables	Operations on lists
Parallelism	-	Two scripts on green flag	Two scripts on key pressed, two scripts on sprite clicked on the same sprite	Two scripts on when I receive message, create clone, two scripts when %s is > %s, two scripts on when backdrop change to
Synchronisation	-	Wait	Broadcast, when I receive message, stop all, stop program, stop programs sprite	Wait until, when backdrop change to, broadcast and wait
Flow Control	-	Sequence of blocks	Repeat, forever	Repeat until
User Interactivity	-	Green flag	Key pressed, sprite clicked, ask and wait,	When %s is >%s, video,

			mouse blocks	audio
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The overall computational thinking score is calculated by adding up the partial scores of each computational thinking concept. So, the computational score ranges from 0 to 21 points. Projects with up to 7 points are considered to prove a basic level of computational thinking, while projects between 8 and 14 points are evaluated as developing, and projects with more than 15 points are marked as master.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Twenty five of participants' final projects were analysed. There were three projects which the Dr Scratch application was not able to analyse. The projects ranged from fruit drop and hide and seek games to animated stories of classics such as Alice in Wonderland, and original animations. All of the projects analysed were evaluated as developing. The average computational thinking score was 10.2 and the median score was 10. The highest scores were achieved in the *synchronisation* and *parallelism* concepts. 84% of the projects scored three out of three in both these concepts. In programming, a thread is like a mini-program within a program that can run at the same time as other programs. A program with multiple threads can do multiple things at once (Parallelism). When programming either games or stories it is useful to separate threads for conceptually distinct tasks. For example, in the ping pong game that Megan and Sylvia designed they spent some time getting the ball to start moving and the clock to start counting down from two minutes at the start of their game. To make their stories as real as possible several groups who were animating stories wanted their programs to do two things at once. For example, in the Alice in Wonderland story animated by Louise and Bernadette, the pupils wanted their character to hide and scream at the same time to create the perception that Alice was falling down the rabbit hole. Including both parallelism and synchronisation in their programs required the pupils to use algorithmic thinking to design a series of instructions to complete a particular task.

Lower scores were achieved in *flow control* in the projects. Although all projects scored at least one point (which required the creation of a sequence of blocks), only 40% of the projects scored more than one out of three. As computers are only able to execute instructions one at a time, there are times when the order of those instructions is important. Sequencing is the specific order in which instructions are performed in an algorithm. Scoring more than one on the flow control concept required the use of iteration. Iteration is the repetition of a sequence of commands (known as a loop). A loop allows for multiple executions of a command without having to create separate code for each execution. Iteration can be either count-controlled or condition-controlled. Count-controlled loops repeat the same steps a specific number of times, regardless of the outcome. The control blocks 'repeat' and 'forever' are examples of count-controlled. A condition-controlled loop will keep repeating the steps over and over, until it gets a specific result. The control block 'repeat until' is an example of a condition-controlled loop. None of the projects contained condition-controlled loops, which is a more advanced programming construct. The projects that contained the count-controlled loops mostly used it for movement in games or stories. The fruit drop game that Sophie and Bethany designed and the pong game that Megan and Sylvia designed both required the sprite (fruit or ball) to move continuously during the game so the forever block was an important construct in their games.

Data Representation (see table 5) was underutilised in student games and animations. Data such as levels, elapsed time, ratings, lives and rewards collected are all examples of more complex data representation. All of the final projects scored one for this concept. In most cases this meant that they tended to assign information about the sprite at the beginning of the game or animation but not make changes to it during the course of the project.

User interactivity was low in all the projects. Again no project scored more than one out of three. The ‘ask and wait’ block allows us to add user interaction to our programs. The question appears in a voice balloon on the screen. Then the program waits as the user types in a response, or until the Enter key is pressed or the check mark is clicked. The program stores the response (user) input in a temporary variable called ‘Answer’. We can then use our answer in the conditional blocks to determine how the program responds. In most cases this was a personal choice, as pupils did not necessarily require user input to determine how the program ran. However, this was a concept which the pupils found difficult when covered in the early sessions.

The lowest score was achieved in the *logic concept*. Only two of the projects achieved any score in the logic concept, and in both cases this was a score of one out of three. This concept is assessed by checking for the presence of certain constructs which cause the program to behave differently depending on certain conditions. These constructs include if, if else and the logical operations; and, or and not. In stories these constructs are not important as stories usually have a linear structure. However, in games these are essential to perform different actions depending on the condition. For example, if the time equals 0, say game over or if touching fruit change score by 1.

LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

At this stage in the research the researchers are engaged in preliminary data analysis. This paper outlines initial findings in respect of one of the three computational thinking dimensions, computational concepts. Findings in relation to the other key dimensions of computational thinking will help to give a clearer picture of computational thinking development. There are several limitations to using Dr Scratch to analyse computational thinking and it is hoped that findings from the other data sources will help to alleviate these limitations. These limitations include:

- The use of a particular block or groups of blocks is not enough to confirm fluency on a certain CT concept.
- The examination of a single project might not be as accurate or complete as the analysis of the collection of projects of the user.
- Some key CT competences cannot be measured by analysing the code of a project, such as the debugging or remixing skills.

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